

Simulation Framework for Radio Resource Management Design in 5G and Beyond Networks

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ABSTRACT

The transition to 5G networks brings significant changes to mobile network architecture. One aspect necessitating reconsideration in the deployment of 5G and beyond networks is the implementation of Radio Resource Management (RRM) procedures. Historically, RRM processes were decentralized at each individual Base Station (BS), with each BS including a scheduler that allocated resources based on requests from client devices served by that BS, utilizing specific frequency-time resource allocation algorithms. The primary task of the scheduler is to ensure maximum spectral efficiency while ensuring fair resource allocation among subscribers. Interaction between BSs and other network elements in terms of RRM is minimized. For example, in case a user is moving between BSs, there is a specified protocol to facilitate seamless subscriber handover between BSs. As a subscriber moves from one BS to another, neighboring BSs exchange information via a certain protocol; during the handover, the scheduler of the first BS removes the subscriber from its schedule, while the scheduler of the second one includes it. Thus, the objective function of the radio resource allocation algorithm in a decentralized system is potentially limited and can only maximize spectral efficiency within cells served by a single BS. Concepts embedded in the architecture of 5G and beyond networks allow for maximizing spectral efficiency (as well as other network key performance indicators) across the entire network using different grades of centralization of RRM management. Full centralization is unlikely to be feasible (at least for large-scale networks) due to strict time constraints on creating scheduling for the next Time Transmission Interval (TTI) in OFDMA systems. In existing networks, scheduling is typically done for a TTI equal to 1 ms for usual mobile traffic, and there are also scenarios with a 125 μ s TTI for low-latency communication applications. It is expected that in further network generations, time constraints will continue to tighten. Despite the fact that scheduling function cannot be moved far from radio transceivers of the Radio Access Network (RAN), maximization of spectral efficiency can be achieved by developing a more holistic RRM design, which uses cooperative data processing from different BSs and is thus able to provide better performance for the entire network as a whole.

One of the main expected ways to upgrade performance is based on the variability of the joint service of one user by several BSs in heterogeneous networks [1]. In situations where the same subscriber can be served in both macro and micro cells of a heterogeneous network, the RRM algorithm potentially can choose the best option considering the communication channel conditions between the subscriber and both BSs, the load of each cell, and other parameters. Another source of heterogeneity is the expectation that 4G, 5G, and beyond 5G networks will coexist and be jointly operated for an extended period. Therefore, the developed RRM management procedures can maximize efficiency by maintaining backward compatibility with standards. There are many other directions for improving RRM efficiency, such as more intelligent subscriber management at cell boundaries in homogeneous networks, more intelligent mobility support, and other mechanisms.

The paper addresses issues in the development of RRM procedures for modern networks, as identified during analysis. While the topic of RRM in mobile networks has been extensively discussed in the literature, most studies focus on pre-5G technologies and single cells in isolation, rather than on holistic network management. In recent years, there has been a shift towards extrapolating known algorithms for use in centralized RANs. However, analysis of such efforts [2, 3] reveals that their implementation is still in its early stages and has yet to deliver a significant advancement in RRM management tasks. Complicating matters is the fact that information regarding the practical implementation of RRM procedures is not publicly disclosed by equipment manufacturers. Most RRM procedures are not specified in any standard and their implementations are proprietary, with manufacturers closely guarding their intellectual property rights, as the algorithms of BS schedulers represent one of their most significant competitive advantages. Thus, there exists a gap between theoretical and practical aspects, between publicly available and proprietary implementations, accompanied by the challenge of evaluating the performance of different RRM procedure implementations. Meanwhile, open-source projects implementing components of 5G RANs currently only offer basic RRM procedures, falling short in efficiency compared to well-developed proprietary solutions. The paradigm shift in the architecture of 5G networks also imposes new requirements on tools necessary for the RRM research and development process. One of the significant changes concerns the software used for simulating the operation of the developed algorithm in RANs, which can no longer operate at the level of individual BSs and must consider multiple processes on a network-wide scale.

To address the challenge of developing efficient RRM algorithms, a simulation system is needed capable of simulating network operation according to usage scenarios and network architecture specified by 3GPP; interacting with the developed RRM algorithm by providing input data for scheduler operation and using the developed schedule for simulation; evaluating the performance of the developed algorithm according to specified efficiency criteria. Several software tools are suitable for simulating RRM development purposes, such as the NS3 Network Simulator, simulators within the OpenAirInterface project, various functionalities within the Matlab 5G Toolbox, etc. However, the analysis conducted revealed that existing simulators usually focus on detailed modeling of a small number of links rather than entire networks. The extensive functionality of these simulators for RRM procedure development purposes at the initial stage is more of a hindrance than an advantage, as it complicates the creation of a system-level simulation model that requires easy scalability and does not require deep detailing. It is worth noting that proprietary simulators, of course, exist, and their capabilities may exceed those of publicly available solutions, but they are inaccessible for research purposes. Thus, one of the important tasks in the RRM research and development process becomes the development of an appropriate simulation tool.

The requirements for developing a system-level simulator were defined by the authors based on practical experience with simulators, guidelines from 3GPP, and a literature review. Comprehensive research on these requirements is presented in the work [4]. The main principle contrasting the developed software with the reviewed simulators above can be formulated as follows: despite the necessity to work with many network elements while developing RRM procedures, the system-level simulator represents the system as a model rather than an exact implementation. This sets it apart from a system-level emulator (for example, OpenAirInterface), which faithfully replicates the majority of system features according to specifications. With a simulator, there is no need to focus on implementing every single function outlined in the 3GPP specifications. Instead, the focus should be on modeling the functionalities and effects that significantly influence performance, i.e., those that determine performance outcomes. Any functionalities deemed to have minimal or no impact on performance, as known or estimated, can be left out or simplified as idealized assumptions.

The simulator, intended for RRM design development in 5G and beyond networks, was developed by the authors according to defined requirements. Its functionality aims to provide the following main features: modeling real network deployments, with a focus mainly on 3GPP release 19 scenarios such as "urban macro," "rural macro," "indoor hotspot," "dense urban," and "broadband access in a crowd"; emulating user traffic models specified for these scenarios; modeling the operation of service categories Enhanced Mobile Broadband (eMBB), Ultra-Reliable and Low Latency Communications (URLLC), and Massive Machine-Type Communications (mMTC); modeling various degrees of network centralization from traditional deployments (baseband units on sites) to fully centralized baseband units pools; modeling heterogeneous networks with cells of different sizes (macrocells + microcells); modeling joint customer service in 4G/5G/Beyond 5G networks; and modeling joint customer service in homogeneous networks on the edges of the cells.

Currently, the simulator focuses on system-level simulation, enabling modeling of semi-centralized RRM procedures on a scale of a small city. The simulator's performance metric evaluates the network's spectral efficiency, with future plans to expand its functionality to assess the network's energy efficiency and computational resource costs. The developed simulator is used in research and development efforts for RRM procedures in 5G and beyond networks. This article's contribution lies in identifying problems in the state of the art, analyzing existing simulation software, formulating requirements, and proposing simulator functionalities.

Keywords: radio resource management, 5G and beyond networks, simulation framework, system-level simulation, semi-centralized radio resource management.

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